

CLIMATE CHANGE AND ENVIRONMENTAL PERFORMANCE IN WESTERN BALKANS

JELENA MINOVIĆ¹, SLAVICA STEVANOVIĆ², AIDA HANIĆ³, PETAR MITIĆ⁴, MILENA KOJIĆ⁵

¹ Institute of Economic Sciences, Belgrade, jelena.minovic@ien.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0001-6254-4888

² Institute of Economic Sciences, Belgrade, slavica.stevanovic@ien.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0002-8545-4540

³ Institute of Economic Sciences, Belgrade, aida.hanic@ien.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0003-4378-7002

⁴ Institute of Economic Sciences, Belgrade, petar.mitic@ien.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0002-7998-9215

⁵ Institute of Economic Sciences, Belgrade, milena.kojic@ien.bg.ac.rs, 0000-0002-6548-5892

Abstract: *The Western Balkan countries are endangered by the climate change effects, and in these economies, climate activism of any kind began later than in the rest of Europe. Moreover, the environmental performance of the Western Balkan region is below the EU average. This paper aims to analyze climate change mitigation in Western Balkan economies. For this purpose, the Environmental Performance Index (EPI) and the ranking for 2024 were used. In this paper, data were obtained through a secondary literature review, including relevant publications, articles, and documents related to the countries of the Western Balkans. The methods used in the paper are analytical and comparative. The results indicate that Albania is the highest-ranked Western Balkan country according to the value of climate change mitigation measured by the EPI index. North Macedonia follows Albania. Then comes Bosnia and Herzegovina, followed by Serbia and Montenegro, respectively. The concluding remarks include recommendations that all Western Balkan economies must enhance their institutions, policies, and capacities because poor governance frequently makes it difficult to enact climate change policies and adapt to the EU environmental acquis. Thus, costlier adaptation measures will result from a lack of systematic planning in response to the climate change effects.*

Keywords: *Climate change mitigation, Environmental performance index, Rank, Western Balkans.*

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